

EFFECT OF AZOTOBACTER ON FIXED NITROGEN

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In previous communications (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 344, 551) it has been observed that only those compounds are utilised by *Azotobacter vinelandii* which are reducible to ammonia. In order to confirm this further, the utilisation of ammonium borate, acetamide, dimethylamine, benzamide, acetanilide and antipyrine has been investigated.

The flasks containing equal volumes of identical solutions of sterile medium inoculated with a culture of *A. vinelandii* containing 10^9 cells per 25 c.c. were kept at 30° and made 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} or $10^{-4}M$ with respect to the substrate by the addition of a suitable volume of the concentrated substrate solution. A known volume of the test solution was withdrawn at intervals and analysed by the usual colorimetric methods.

Ammonium Borate.—Ammonium sulphate was shown to be utilised (*Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1955, 18, 363) but the utilisation stopped after a certain stage due to the liberation of H_2SO_4 which arrested the bacterial growth. Therefore ammonium borate, a salt of a weak acid, was tried to see if it could be completely utilised. Two concentrations of ammonium borate were studied ($10^{-2}M$ to $10^{-3}M$). The amount of the substrate was estimated colorimetrically in samples withdrawn at intervals with Nessler's reagent; for the more concentrated solution the method gave satisfactory results, but with more dilute solutions the colour did not develop. It was observed that ammonium borate, just like other ammonium salts, was utilised after a certain lag period (Table I).

Acetamide.—Acetamide being acidic in aqueous solution was dissolved in phosphate buffer (KH_2PO_4 and K_2HPO_4) to adjust its pH to 7.2-7.4, being the condition for optimum growth of azotobacter. The concentrations of the amide studied were 10^{-1} to $10^{-3}M$. The concentration of the amide was determined colorimetrically in samples withdrawn at intervals with hydroxylamine sulphate, followed by the addition of ferric chloride solution in HCl. Acetamide was found to be utilised after a certain lag period.

Diethylamine.—The concentrations studied in the present work ranged from $10^{-1}M$ to $10^{-3}M$ as there was no colour developed with the lower concentrations. The concentrations of the amine were determined colorimetrically in samples withdrawn at intervals with 1% solution of sodium nitroprusside, followed by the addition of acetaldehyde. The amine was not utilised by the bacteria as it was found to be toxic at these concentrations.

Benzamide.—Benzamide being in aqueous solution was dissolved in phosphate buffer (KH_2PO_4 and K_2HPO_4) to adjust its pH to 7.2. Three concentrations of the amide studied ranged from 10^{-1} to $10^{-3}M$. The amount of the benzamide was estimated colorimetrically in samples withdrawn at intervals with an alkaline solution of

hydroxylamine sulphate, followed by the addition of acidified ferric chloride which developed a violet-red colour. It was observed that the benzamide was not utilised just like other aromatic organic compounds.

Acetanilide was also tried in concentrations ranging from 10^{-1} to $10^{-3}M$ and it was observed that it was not utilised by the bacteria.

TABLE I
% Utilisation.

Time.	Ammonium borate.		Acetanilide.		
	$10^{-3}M.$	$10^{-2}M.$	$10^{-1}M.$	$10^{-2}M.$	$10^{-3}M.$
0 hr.	...	...	...	...	...
1	...	...	...	...	...
2	...	...	...	...	...
3	5	...	...	...	...
4	23	...	...	...	...
5	39	...	...	...	...
6	56	...	...	...	...
7	73	...	...	...	...
8	86	...	...	...	...
9	100	0	...	...	...
10	...	11	...	...	...
11	...	25	...	...	...
12	...	38	...	...	...
13	...	50	...	...	...
14	...	64	...	...	...
15	...	78	...	...	...
16	...	93	...	...	...
19	...	...	0	...	...
20	...	...	8	...	...
22	...	...	23.0	...	...
24	...	...	42.0	0	...
25	...	...	...	5.0	...
26	...	...	58.0	...	...
28	...	...	76.0	28.0	0
29	...	...	...	...	5.0
30	...	...	94.0	42.0	12.0
31	...	...	100.0	...	18.0
32	...	...	...	58.0	...
33	...	...	...	...	32.0
34	...	...	...	70.0	...
35	...	...	...	...	44.0
36	...	...	...	84.0	...
37	...	...	...	...	54.0
38	...	...	...	100.0	...
39	...	...	...	...	68.0
41	...	...	...	...	80.0
42	...	...	...	...	94.0
43	...	...	...	...	...

Antipyrine was tried in concentrations ranging from $10^{-3}M$ to $10^{-4}M$. The concentrations at various intervals of time were determined colorimetrically by adding 1% ferric chloride solution. It was observed that even after 48 hours there was no sign of its utilisation by the bacteria and at the same time it was not found to be toxic.

As a result of all the above experiments it has been observed that the ammonium salts are utilised but the aromatic compounds containing $CONH_2$ in the nucleus or the side chain are not utilised by the *A. vinelandii* even if they are not toxic. This confirms the view that only those nitrogenous compounds are utilised which are reduceable to ammonia, which indirectly points to the conclusion that ammonia is the intermediate product in nitrogen fixation.

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